

CONCEPT MAPPING AND VEE MAPPING: INSTRUCTIONAL TOOLS FOR EFFECTIVE TEACHING OF BIOLOGY TOWARDS IMPROVING SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AND ATTITUDE IN TARABA STATE NIGERIA

Bakari Henry Gideon¹, Fatima Mohammed Joda², & R. O. Ugwuadu³

¹ Department of Biology Education, School of Undergraduate Studies, College of Education Zing

^{2,3} Environmental and Life Sciences Education, Faculty of Education, Modibbo Adamawa University Yola

Corresponding Author: bakarihenry341@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10414491>

Abstract

The study investigated the effects of concept-mapping and vee-mapping instructional strategies on biology students' academic achievement and attitude in senior secondary school in Taraba state, Nigeria. Two research questions and two hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted quasi-experimental pretest, posttest and post-post test, non-equivalent, experimental and control groups. The population of the study consisted of 11,837 senior secondary schools in Taraba state. The sample comprised of 154 students in intact classes randomly assigned for experimental groups and control groups. An instrument used for data collection was an Achievement Test tagged Biology Achievement Test (BAT) and Biology Students' Attitude Scale Questionnaire (BSASQ). The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistics for the research questions and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to test the null hypotheses. The study revealed students performed high using Concept-mapping and Vee-mapping teaching strategies than in lecture method in biology. It was recommended that biology teachers should adopt concept-mapping and vee-mapping teaching strategy as an effective learning strategy in order to improve students' academic achievement and social interaction skills.

Keywords: Concept-mapping, Vee-mapping, Academic Achievement, Attitude

Introduction

Education is a process that is very important for the success of an individual in the society. It is a process that provides learners with the knowledge and skills that prepares them for future contribution to societal development. It is through education that the desired societal changes are achieved (Kenneth, 2013). It has the purpose of preparing the individual with what is necessary to be productive and contribute positively to one's society (Nnoli, 2016). Recently there has been increasing awareness of the importance of learner centeredness in the teaching-learning Process. This has drawn a lot of attention in relation to understanding how learners learn and how to help them learn about concepts. The new global order in science education curriculum which came as a result of explosion in knowledge and the corresponding progress in technology, demands qualitative and functional approaches to teaching and learning processes (Gbadamosi, 2013). It consequently brings to light that the yardstick that characterizes the world into developed and developing countries are the level and quality of science education which is achieved through effective science teaching of the young generation.

Biology as a science as scientific is a core subject taught at all levels of our educational systems, from pre-primary to tertiary levels. Citing Kara and Rogers (2012), Obioha and Danjuma (2021) maintain that Biology encompasses diverse fields, including botany, conservation, ecology, evolution, genetics, marine biology, medicine and zoology. Although the subject is a prerequisite to these courses, poor achievement in the subject is alarming. Educators in the field of Biology have advocated for the use of the constructivist that would make learning more meaningful through students' active participation (Mwanda, Odundo, & Midigo 2017, Dogra 2021). Information from the Taraba state ministry of basic and secondary education resource centre Jalingo on statistics of students' WAEC achievement in biology for the past eight years 2011-2019 shows achievement has not been consistent but fluctuates and in some years the failure rate is very alarming- 2013 (32.5%), 2015 (83.16%) and 2019 (21.75%). This disturbing trend requires close investigation by educators.

Several factors have been pointed out as the reasons for poor achievement of students in Biology by different researchers. One of such factors aside others is the methods used in teaching the subject (Manalanga & Awelani, 2014). Sakiyo and Waziri, (2015) maintain that there is need for the students to be given a more realistic teaching approach that will cushion and fasten their ability to learn new concepts with students' learning manners. Biology teachers are therefore encouraged to exploit a host of teaching and learning strategies that move away from the traditional method of teaching which is teacher-centered.

One of the important factors in learning Biology as a science subject is students' attitude. Positive students' attitudes can motivate students' interest in biology and other science subjects. It is a common understanding among science educationist that students' achievement in science subjects is a function of their attitude. According to Namasaka (2009), male students were found to have more positive attitudes towards all the aspects of science apart from the perception of science as a male domain. Female students were found to be affected by stereotypes regarding science subjects as a male domain. Nasr and Asghar (2011) in their study established that, there was no significant difference between girls and boys in attitude towards biology, although girls had better achievements in biology in comparison with boys. All these point to the fact that a better and effective approach to teaching science subjects is needed to make lesson delivery easy and exciting to the students in order to draw the needed attitude to the subject.

Scientists and science educators have been searching for more realistic approach to teach science due to the issue of decline in students' achievement. Canas and Novak (2009) describe concept-maps as graphical tools for organizing and representing knowledge. They include concepts, usually enclosed in circles or boxes and relationships between the concepts are indicated by linking the two concepts with a line. Words on the line are referred to as the linking phrases and specify the relationship between two concepts. It is a graphical tool that scientist, designers, engineers, technical writers and others use to organize and structure knowledge. Concept-mapping is a means of developing logical thinking and study skills by revealing connections and helping students to see how individual ideas form a larger whole. The method has been identified to promote understanding of science concepts; hence many studies have been and are still being conducted on this teaching approach. The extent to which concept-mapping could influence students' achievement in Biology is consequently worth investigating.

Teaching and learning science requires understanding of concepts through assimilation of new ones into existing concepts. In cognizance of the complexity and tedious task of teaching concepts, Novak and Gowin (1984) as cited by Wahidin and Meerah (2013) stated that, to complement the advantages offered by concept-mapping in navigating students towards meaningful learning, another thinking tool known as vee-map was introduced. The strategy provides a visual structure for an experiment or study, providing a basis for both theoretical and conceptual content, but also for analysis, processing,

interpretation and reflection (Cziprok & Popescu, 2014). It is one way to organize the process of solving an interesting problem (Supranto & Rahmawati, 2017). Evren, Bati and Yilmaz (2012) commenting on vee-mapping as a teaching tool, explained that vee-mapping can be used in educational environment to foster students thinking skills and enable them to use such thinking skills as well as constructing attitude for deeper thinking. A study on this strategy by Njue and Magana (2016) found that Vee Heuristics Teaching Approach (VHTA) facilitated Students' achievements in biology regardless of gender. According to Novak and Canas (2006), vee-mapping is an epistemological tool that guides the analyses and illustrates the interplay between the conceptual (thinking) elements like philosophizing, theorizing, identifying principles and conceptualization, and also the methodological elements such as, recording, transforming, knowledge claims and value claims in the context of an educative event to answer some focus questions. Kyere (2019) submitted that students use vee-shaped maps to represent key elements (ideas) that are contained in the structure of knowledge.

Unlike Concept-map and Vee-map teaching strategies, lecture method is a widely used instructional approach. It is a method used primarily to introduce students to new concepts, but it is also a valuable method of summarizing ideas, showing relationships between theories and practice, and re-emphasizing the main points. Commenting on the pitfalls of this method, Odili (2011) stated that lecture method emphasizes presenting ideas and information by the teachers to the learners without involving the learners in the learning process. Many teachers use the method almost exclusively, as it is considered the simplest, enabling one to cover large amount of material in a short period of time (Abdullahi, 2012). The problem with this method of teaching is that, teachers use prematurely verbal techniques that are monotonous, often scattered and incoherent, with students having no cognitive readiness to learn meaningfully (Valadares, 2013). However, one could point out that, this method of teaching has the advantage of enabling the teacher to handle a large content of the syllabus within a short period of time.

Statement of Problem

Over the years studies carried out by experts in science education indicates persistent students' low level of achievement in biology at the various public examinations in Nigeria. This has continued to attract the attention of major stakeholders in education. Available statistics from the West African Examination Council (WAEC) from 2010-2020 indicates that, students' achievement in biology at the senior secondary school level has not been consistent but continues to fluctuate over the years 2013 (32.5%), 2015 (83.16%) and 2019 (21.75%). More worrisome is the fact that this unimpressive trend means students might find it difficult to transit to tertiary institutions and gaining meaningful employment opportunities in the state and the country at large. This trend in pattern of achievement in public examinations might be an indicator of poor teaching approach by teachers and poor attitude with little interest in the subject by the students.

It is obvious that teaching some biological concepts can be difficult because of their abstract nature, lack of instructional aids and complexity of some topics. This situation calls for alternative methods of teaching that could lead to meaningful and effective learning outcome. Concept-mapping and Vee-mapping teaching strategies have been identified as recent approaches in teaching that could be useful tools for processing, organizing and presenting information graphically and alluded facilitate meaningful learning among students. Consequently, it is in view of this that this study was designed to explore the comparative advantage of Concept-mapping and Vee-mapping teaching strategies over that of the traditional lecture method in teaching some topics in Biology. The study determined their effects on academic achievement and attitude

of the students to the subject in Taraba state. The study also went further to investigate the effects of gender disparity on academic achievement and attitude in the course of using these teaching strategies.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to investigate the effects of concept-mapping and vee-mapping teaching strategies on senior secondary school students’ academic achievement and attitude to biology in Taraba State. Specifically, the study determined the:

1. Effect of Concept-Mapping and Vee-Mapping teaching strategies and Lecture method on academic achievement of senior secondary school Biology students in Taraba state.
2. Effect of Concept-Mapping and Vee-Mapping teaching strategies and lecture method on attitude of senior secondary school Biology students in Taraba state.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What are the pre-test and post-test mean achievement scores of senior secondary school students taught biology with Concept-mapping and Vee-mapping teaching strategies and those taught with lecture method in Taraba state?
2. What are the pre-test and post-test mean attitude scores of senior secondary school students taught biology with Concept-mapping and Vee-mapping teaching strategies and those taught with Lecture method in Taraba state?

Hypotheses

The study tested two null hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level of significance.

HO₁ There is no statistically significant main effect of Concept-mapping, Vee-mapping teaching strategies and lecture method on senior secondary school students’ academic achievement in Biology in Taraba state.

HO₂ There is no statistically significant main effect of Concept-mapping, Vee-mapping teaching strategies and lecture method on senior secondary school students’ attitude to Biology in Taraba state.

Methodology

The research design used for this study was pre-test post-test, quasi-experimental control group design. The treatment was at three levels; which are concept-mapping, vee-mapping teaching strategies and lecture method as independent variables. Students’ academic achievement and attitude were the dependent variables. This design was used because it permits purposive sampling of students into groups since the students were in their regular intact classes such that normal school activities were not be interrupted, and also, it enables the control of extraneous variables. It consisted of three groups containing experimental group I and II and a control group. All the three groups were given a pre-test before the commencement of the lessons. Experimental group I was taught using concept-mapping; group II was exposed to teaching using Vee-mapping. The control group was taught the same topics using the traditional lecture method of teaching. The design for the study is illustrated in the diagram below.

EGI	O1	X1	O2
EGII	O3	X2	O4
CG	O5	C	O6

Where EGI and EGII represent Experimental groups one and two respectively. While CG is the control group.

O1, O3, O5 represent pre –test observation; and O2, O4, O6, represent post- test.

XI represents treatment with concept- mapping teaching strategy.

X2 represent treatment with vee-mapping teaching strategy.

C represents treatment with lecture method in the control group.

The study population consisted of 11,837 senior secondary II school students in the 2020/2021 academic session in Taraba state. The sample population was 154 students from three educational zones. The instruments used for collecting data about students’ academic achievement and attitude to Biology were a Biology Achievement Test (BAT) adopted from Patrick (2018) and a five point likert scale on Biology Students’ attitude Scale Questionnaire (BSASQ) adopted from Prokop (2007)

The two research questions were analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation. Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the two hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis was rejected when $p < 0.05$ level of significance or otherwise if $p > 0.05$ level of significance. The decision rule for the Biology Students’ Attitude Scale Questionnaire (BSASQ) was: Strongly Agree=5, Agree=4, Undecided=3, Disagree=2, strongly Disagree=1. Any mean score of 3.50 and above was considered positive attitude towards Biology, 3.49 and below were negative attitude towards the subject.

Results

Research Question 1. What are the pre-test and post-test mean achievement scores of senior secondary school students taught biology with concept-mapping, vee-mapping teaching strategies and those taught with lecture method in Taraba state?

Table 1: Mean And Standard Deviation of Pre-Test and Post-Test Mean Achievement Scores of Senior Secondary School Students Taught Biology with Concept-Mapping, Vee-Mapping Teaching Strategies and those Taught with Lecture Method in Taraba State.

Teaching strategies	n	Pretest		Posttest	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Concept-mapping	49	42.29	12.69	45.18	13.83
Vee-mapping	50	34.80	11.69	41.48	13.79
Lecture Method	53	38.11	14.66	34.98	12.09

The descriptive statistics in table 2 revealed that, concept-mapping group with 49 students has a pretest mean achievement score of 42.29 and standard deviation of 12.69. In the posttest achievement score, concept-mapping group has the highest mean achievement score of 45.18 with a standard deviation of 13.83. The Vee-mapping group with 50 students has a pretest mean achievement score of 34.80 and standard deviation of 11.69. In the posttest achievement score, Vee-mapping group has the mean achievement score of 41.48 with a standard deviation of 13.79. The conventional Lecture group with 53 students has a pretest mean achievement score of 38.11 and standard deviation of 14.66. In the posttest achievement conventional Lecture group has the mean achievement score of 34.98 with a standard deviation of 12.09. In summary, the mean difference between pretest and posttest is high which means the three teaching strategies were equally important at improving students’ achievement at different levels.

Research Question 2: What are the pre-test and post-test mean attitude scores of senior secondary school students taught biology with concept-map, Vee-map teaching methods and those taught with lecture method in Taraba state?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Pre-Test and Post-Test Mean Attitude Scores of Senior Secondary School Students Taught Biology with Concept-Mapping, Vee-Mapping Teaching Strategies and those Taught with Lecture Method in Taraba State

Teaching strategies	n	Pretest		Posttest	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Concept-mapping	49	69.24	4.11	92.31	5.94
Vee-Mapping	50	69.60	7.28	88.88	5.11
Lecture method	53	68.53	6.06	90.30	5.78

The descriptive statistics in Table 2 revealed that, concept map group with 49 students has a pretest mean attitude score of 69.24 and standard deviation of 4.11. In the post-test attitude score, concept-map group has the highest mean attitude score of 92.31 with a standard deviation of 5.94. The Vee map group with 50 students has a pretest mean attitude score of 69.60 and standard deviation of 7.28. In the posttest attitude score, Vee map group has the mean attitude score of 88.86 with a standard deviation of 5.11. The conventional lecture group with 53 students has a pretest mean attitude score of 68.53 and standard deviation of 6.06. In the posttest attitude score conventional lecture group has the mean attitude score of 90.30 with a standard deviation of 5.78. However, concept-mapping teaching strategy showed slightly better improvement in attitude followed by lecture method and Vee-mapping respectively.

HO₁ There is no statistically significant main effect of Concept-mapping, Vee-mapping teaching strategies and lecture method on senior secondary school students’ achievement in Biology in Taraba state.

Table 3: ANCOVA Table of Main Effect of Concept-Mapping, Vee-Mapping Teaching Strategies and Lecture Method on Senior Secondary School Students’ Academic Achievement in Biology in Taraba State.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared	Eta
Corrected Model	3306.705 ^a	3	1102.235	5.682	.001	.103	
Intercept	20584.853	1	20584.853	106.121	.000	418	
PRETEST	263.486	1	263.486	1.358	.246	.009	
Teaching_Strategies	2523.172	2	1261.586	6.504	.002	.081	
Error	28708.235	148	193.975				
Total	278023.000	152					
Corrected Total	32014.941	151					

a. R Squared = .103 (Adjusted R Squared = .085)

The results of the analysis in Table 3 revealed that, there is significant difference in academic achievement of senior secondary school students taught biology with concept-mapping, vee-mapping teaching strategies and lecture method $F = 6.50$ ($df\ 2, 151$), $P = 0.00$. Since the computed p-value (0.001) is less than 0.05 level of significant, therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is rejected and concluded that, there is significant difference in academic achievement of senior secondary school students taught biology with concept-mapping, vee-mapping teaching strategies and lecture method in favour of concept-mapping and vee-mapping method. The partial eta square of 0.081 shows that 8.1% of students' academic achievement is attributed to the treatments, Concept-mapping and Vee-mapping teaching strategies.

Table 4 Bonferroni Multiple Comparison Analysis Table of Main Effect of Concept-Mapping, Vee-Mapping Teaching Strategies and Lecture Method on Senior Secondary School Students' Academic Achievement in Biology in Taraba State.

(I) Teach.Strats	(J) Teach,Strats	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Concept-Mapping	Vee-Mapping	3.70	2.66	0.02	-1.55	8.96
	Lecture Method	10.20	2.62	0.00	5.01	15.38
Vee-Mapping	Concept-Mapping	-3.70	2.66	0.16	-8.96	1.55
	Lecture Method	6.49	2.60	0.01	1.34	11.65
Lecture Method	Concept-Mapping	-10.20	2.62	0.00	-15.38	-5.01
	Vee-Mapping	-6.49	2.60	0.01	-11.6	-1.34

Table 4 showed the results of Bonferroni Multiple Comparisons of treatments. The result revealed that there is a significant mean difference in academic achievement between concept-mapping and vee-mapping teaching strategies ($p = 0.02$) with a mean difference of 3.70 in favour of concept map. There is also a significant difference between concept-mapping strategy and lecture method ($p = 0.00$) with a mean difference of 10.20 in favour of concept-mapping strategy. There is a significant difference between vee-mapping strategy and lecture method ($p = 0.01$) with a mean difference of 6.49 in favour of vee-mapping strategy. The result indicated that, concept-mapping group performed better than vee-mapping strategy and lecture method groups while, Vee-mapping strategy group performed better than lecture group.

HO₂: There is no statistically significant main effect of Concept-mapping, Vee-mapping teaching strategies and lecture method on senior secondary school students' attitude to Biology in Taraba state.

Table 5 ANCOVA Table of Main Effect of Concept-Mapping, Vee-Mapping Teaching Strategies and Lecture Method on Senior Secondary School Students’ Attitude to Biology in Taraba State.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	392.052 ^a	3	130.684	4.159	.007	.078
Intercept	9464.862	1	9464.862	301.245	.000	.671
PRE_ATTITUDE	78.514	1	78.514	2.499	.116	.017
TEACHING_METHODS	315.396	2	157.698	5.019	.008	.064
Error	4650.027	148	31.419			
Total	1244536.000	152				
Corrected Total	5042.079	151				

a. R Squared = .078 (Adjusted R Squared = .059)

The results of the analysis in Table 5 revealed that, there is significant difference in attitude of senior secondary school students taught biology with concept-mapping, vee-mapping teaching strategies and lecture method $F = 5.019$ (df_2 151), $P = 0.008$. Since the computed p-value (0.008) is less than 0.05 level of significant, therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is rejected and concluded that, there is significant difference in attitude of senior secondary school students taught biology with concept-mapping, vee-mapping teaching strategies and lecture method in favour of concept-mapping and vee-mapping teaching strategies. The partial eta square of 0.064 indicates that 6.4% of the students’ attitude to Biology is attributed to the effect of concept-mapping and Vee-mapping teaching strategies.

Discussion of Findings

Descriptive statistics and hypothesis testing presents interesting result. The result indicates that all the groups had shown increment in academic achievement, and attitude mean scores after being exposed to the treatments. This shows that both experimental groups had a significant knowledge increment about the topics taught with concept-mapping and vee-mapping teaching strategies. The positive effect of these teaching strategies indicates that the overall framework of the concepts being learned was made explicit by the teaching strategies which ensured better organisation of the material presented by both the students and the teachers during the lessons which promoted meaningful learning.

Also, there is significant change in achievement of students in Biology when exposed to the treatments with concept-mapping having the highest posttest mean difference followed by vee-mapping and the least is Lecture method. Bilesanmi (2021) found that the concept-mapping strategy is more effective in enhancing students’ achievement in biology than the lecture method. Musa, Bernadette and Veronica, (2018) after studying the effect of Vee-map on gender and students’ achievement found no significant difference between the post-test achievements irrespective of gender. Studying Vee-mapping teaching strategy, Njue and Magana (2016) who found that Vee Heuristics Teaching Approach (VHTA) facilitated Students’ achievements in biology regardless of gender. This implies that given equal opportunity in the learning process, and when taught with these strategies (concept-mapping and vee-mapping) influence on academic achievement of the students.

Similarly, the study found that there is statistical main effect of attitude toward biology when the students were taught with Concept-map and Vee-map teaching strategies. This also agrees with a study by Njue, Kamau and Mwaina (2018) established that Vee-heuristics teaching approach (VHTA) facilitates positive students’ attitude towards biology subject-irrespective of gender and type of school attended. When the experimental groups were compared with the control group,

concept-mapping has a better impact on students' attitude towards Biology than vee-mapping teaching strategy with lecture method having the least impact.

Conclusion

Base on the findings of this study, it could be deduced that concept-mapping teaching strategy compared with Vee-mapping teaching strategy could encourage better positive effect on achievement of students in the teaching of Biological concepts. Vee-mapping can foster better effect on the students when compared to lecture method. The two teaching strategies could also impact positively on students' attitude toward biology.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher made the following recommendations.

1. Teachers should be encouraged to adapt the use of Concept-mapping and Vee-mapping teaching strategies to make the teaching of Biology more meaningful and less stressful in the understanding of concepts that would have been difficult to achieve when taught with lecture method.
2. Biology textbook authors should fashion book contents to be in line with the constructivist approach which emphasizes student centered approach. This study has revealed such potential in Concept-mapping and Vee-mapping teaching strategies compared to the traditional lecture method.

References

- Abdullahi, A. (2012). An Investigation into Status of Primary Science Teaching in Nigeria. *Journal of Science Teachers Association of Nigeria*, 20 (2), 193-200.
- Bilesanmi, A, J.B. (2021).Concept – Mapping, Students' Locus of Control and Gender as Determinants of Nigerian High School Students' Achievement in Biology. Retrieved March 2021 from <https://journals.co.za/doi/pdf/10.10520/EJC38530>
- Cziprok,C & Popescu,F.F. (2014).Using the Vee -heuristic in Laboratory Classroom for Teaching and Learning Physics of Photonic Devices, (Paper Presented at the Annual Session of Faculty of Physics University of Bucharest Magurele, Romania).
- Dogra,B (2021).Constructivist Classroom Activities for Biology Learning Retrieved March 2021 from <https://journals.co.za/doi/pdf/10.10520/EJC38530>
- Evren, A, Bati, K, &Yilmaz, S. (2012).The effect of using V-diagrams in Science and Facilitate Meaningful Learning. *Instructional Science*. (19), 29-52.
- Gbadamosi, A.F. (2013). Awareness and Utilisation of Innovative Teaching strategies in Oyo South Senatorial District,(Unpublished Med Thesis University of Ilorin Nigeria).
- Kenneth, C, A. (2013). Effect of Concept Mapping Instructional Strategy on Students' Retention in Biology. *African Education Indices*, 5 (1), 1-8.
- Kyere, I & Ameyaw, Y. (2019). Mapping Biological Concepts :Concept-Vee maps an improver of students performance in photosynthesis. *International Journal of Innovative Research &Technology*, 6 (6), 169-181.
- Manalanga, C. I. & Awelani, V.M. (2014). Exploring Factors Affecting Achievement in Biology at selected High Schools in Lesotho. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*.5(8),271-278.

- Mwanda, G, Odundo, P & Midigo, R. (2017). Towards Adoption of Constructivist Instructional Approach in Learning Biology in Secondary School Students in Kenya: Addressing Learner Attitude, *International Journal of Secondary Education*, 5(1) 1-11.
- Namasaka, F.W. (2009). Effect of Concept-map and vee-mapping Strategy on students' Motivation and Achievement in Biology in Secondary Schools. Unpublished M.Ed Thesis Egerton University Kenya.
- Nasr, A.R. (2011). Attitude towards Biology and its Effect on Students Achievement. *International Journal of Biology*, 3(4), 100-104.
- Njue, A, K & Mwaina, K (2018). The Effects of V-heuristics on secondary school students attitude towards Biology in Kenya, *Journal of Research and Method in Education*, 8(1), 18-23.
- Njue, A, K & Magana, A.M. (2016). Effects of Vee Heuristic Teaching Approach on Achievement of Boys and Girls in Biology in Public Secondary Schools in Kenya, *International Journal of Education and Research*, 4(10).
- Novak, J. D. (1984). Learning, Creating and using Knowledge: Concept-Map as Facilitative Tools in Schools and Corporations. *Journal of Learning and Knowledge Society*, 6(3), 21-30.
- Obioha, N.C. & Danjuma, G.S. (2021). Impact of Biology Terminologies Subsumers on Secondary School Students' Achievement in Jalingo Education Zone, Taraba State, Nigeria. *Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Science*, 9 (1), 62-68.
- Odili, A.O. (2011). *Mathematics in Nigeria's Secondary Schools; a Teaching Prospective*. Portharcourt: Achuna Educational Books.
- Sakiyo, J. & Waziri, K. (2015). Concept mapping strategy: An effective tool for improving Students' Academic Achievement in biology. *Journal of Education in Science, Environment and Health (JESEH)*, 1(1), 56-62.
- Supranto, P.K & Rahmawati, L. (2017). The influence of V Diagram on Animal Ecology Lab to Learning Outcome and Logical Thinking. *Journal of Education*. 2(2), 2579-8383.
- Valadares, J. (2013). Concept maps and the Meaningful Learning of Science. *Journal for Educators, Teachers and Trainers*, (4), 164-179.
- Wahidin, K.O, & Meerah, S.M. (2013). Concept Mapping in Chemistry Lessons: Tools for Inculcating Thinking Skills in Chemistry Learning. *Journal of Baltic Science Education*, 12 (5), 668.
- West African Examination Council (WAEC) May/June 2011- 2020 State committee meeting Chief Examiner's report.